

PAAW: PORTABLE ASSISTANT FOR ANIMAL WELFARE, A DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM FOR THE PROVINCIAL VETERINARY SERVICES OFFICE OF NUEVA VIZCAYA

Camille Jesmin B. Naces, Hendre Leigh O. Sagabaen, Melbraei B. Santiago, Angel Hamelton O. Yacapin, Rocel Audrey J. Batara, MIT

ABSTRACT

The Portable Assistant for Animal Welfare (PAAW) is an innovative support system designed for the Provincial Veterinary Services Office of Nueva Vizcaya. Developed using the MERN stack (MongoDB, Express, React, Node.js), PAAW is a single-page progressive web application (PWA) aimed at enhancing operational efficiency across core divisions, including Livestock and Poultry Development, Animal Healthcare and Management, Regulatory and Monitoring, and Administrative functions. The system was created following the Rapid Application Development (RAD) methodology, emphasizing iterative prototyping to ensure a user-centered, responsive, and functional platform. PAAW integrates several key features, such as streamlined data collection, offline accessibility through CSV export, and data visualization using Chart.js, which enables users to analyze and manage information efficiently. Its architecture leverages cloud storage, providing flexible data handling capabilities and ensuring seamless functionality for both desktop and mobile users. The system was evaluated by 13 participants, comprising 4 administrative personnel, 7 operational staff from various divisions, and 2 IT experts. Their feedback confirmed that PAAW effectively addresses the practical needs of its users. An ISO 25010:2015 assessment was conducted, yielding an overall mean score of 4.40, which indicates a high degree of compliance with the quality characteristics outlined in the standard. This result demonstrates that PAAW successfully meets its specified requirements and delivers a robust and efficient solution for veterinary service operations.

Keywords: Animal welfare, decision support system, veterinary services, MERN stack, progressive web application

RATIONALE

In today's world, technology is a fundamental part of daily life, integrated into nearly every aspect of our activities throughout the day. One of the reasons why technology, regardless of discipline, has been a focus for professionals and stakeholders is that it makes daily activities more convenient while saving time and enhancing the quality of life (Simplilearn, 2022). IT is essential to modern business and organizational operations because it allows for automated data-handling procedures that increase productivity, promote efficiency, and grant competitive advantages, especially in the marketplace. The development and integration of information systems (IS), which use digital technologies to simplify data administration, ease decision-making, and maximize operational effectiveness, has been prompted by the increasing reliance on IT in contemporary business operations.

Information systems are essential to decision-making because they give decision-makers access to fast, accurate, and pertinent information. These systems aid in the gathering, processing, and display of data in a manner that facilitates wise decision-making. Organizations can use information systems to streamline their decision-making procedures, increase productivity, lower uncertainty, and eventually accomplish their strategic objectives (Khalid, 2019). Information systems (IS) highlight the importance of using data to inform decisions in the current corporate

environment. This is a crucial technique for staying competitive and succeeding in the market, particularly for businesses that don't see the value in information systems.

This study is critical for the PVSU of Nueva Vizcaya, the Provincial Veterinary Services Office of Nueva Vizcaya since it represents the transition from outdated paper-based processes to modern digital solutions. By embracing technology, the office can streamline administrative operations, improve data management and analysis, foster employee cooperation, and increase overall efficiency and productivity. These digital advancements led to a more efficient, well-organized, and accurate operational process, which significantly enhanced PVSU's productivity and service quality.

The study provides significant insights and recommendations to the administration of the Provincial Veterinary Services Office of Nueva Vizcaya, assisting them with strategic planning and resource efficiency. The administration can make policy creation and program implementation decisions based on the study's findings, which create clear objectives and priorities. By implementing the study's recommended procedures and documentation requirements, the administration may increase accountability and transparency inside the office, increasing public trust and confidence in its operations.

To the **Staff** of the Provincial Veterinary Services Office of Nueva Vizcaya, moving away from paper-based processes represents a big potential to streamline workflows and save time for employees. Embracing digital solutions allowed employees to focus on providing high-quality services rather than getting bogged down by administrative duties. This change not only increases productivity but also generates a more efficient and dynamic work atmosphere, allowing employees to serve the needs of the community better.

To the **Community**, the community of Nueva Vizcaya was greatly impacted by the system's deployment. The system improves the community's capacity to care for its livestock and animals by making veterinary services more easily available and effective. By fostering the expansion and sustainability of the agriculture industry, this advancement not only advances the health and welfare of animals but also advances the region's overall economic development.

The researchers aim to develop a Veterinary System for the Provincial Veterinary Service Office of Nueva Vizcaya, known as PAAW: Portable Assistant for Animal Welfare, which represents a significant advancement from manual, paper-based processes to a computerized recording system. PAAW aims to enhance animal welfare practices and operational efficiency within the office through several key features. It streamlines patient registration procedures, reducing errors and increasing efficiency in capturing and managing patient data. Additionally, PAAW transitions client record management from paper-based files to digital databases, improving data accessibility and facilitating seamless communication among veterinary staff. The system includes a decision support component, providing real-time access to clinical guidelines and treatment protocols to inform evidence-based decision-making.

Figure 1
Conceptual Framework

Statement of the Problem

This capstone project, "PAAW: A Portable Assistant for Animal Welfare," aimed to solve the operational problems faced by the Provincial Veterinary Services Office (PVSO) of Nueva Vizcaya. The goal was to modernize the PVSO's record-keeping and operations with a digital support system. This system helped streamline data management, improved the accuracy of field reports, and enhanced the monitoring and control of livestock diseases. The project addressed the issues of the current paper-based system, which caused delays, errors, and inefficient resource management. By implementing a digital solution, the aim was to make administrative tasks easier and provide useful information for better decision-making in animal welfare and public health. The study began in the 2nd semester of S.Y. 2023-2024 with the writing of the rationale and research methodology and continued into the 1st semester of S.Y. 2024-2025 for data gathering and system development, which was expected to be completed by December 2024, thus spanning from January to December. This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the current problem of the Provincial Veterinary Service Office (PVSO) based on their current practices in terms of their:
 - A. Data Management
 - Administrative Personnel
 - Livestock and Poultry Development
 - Regulatory and Monitoring
 - Animal Health Care and Management
 - B. Decision-making on the gathered data from:
 - Field reports,
 - Inventory reports
2. What system would be developed to solve those problems?
3. What is the extent to which the PAAW decision support system complies with ISO 25010?
 - A. Functional Suitability
 - B. Performance Efficiency
 - C. Compatibility
 - D. Usability
 - E. Reliability
 - F. Security
 - G. Maintainability, and Portability

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research entitled "PAAW: Portable Assistant for Animal Welfare, a Decision Support System for the Provincial Veterinary Services Office of Nueva Vizcaya" uses a mixed-methods approach that combines both descriptive and developmental methods. Descriptive methods are used to gather complete data on the current challenges encountered by the Provincial Veterinary Service Office (PVSO) of Nueva Vizcaya and evaluate the completed system. In contrast, developmental methods focus on the utilization of a developmental model to follow in the proper development of the system. Both of these approaches were utilized to gather data and develop and evaluate the developed system.

Research Locale

The Provincial Veterinary Services Office of Nueva Vizcaya (PVSO) offers a wide range of essential services to support livestock health and farming in the province. By focusing on livestock quality and health, PVSO aims to improve farming productivity and enhance the agricultural sector. These services play a crucial role in helping farmers maintain healthy livestock, which benefits both the local economy and the overall quality of farming practices in the region. A key service provided by PVSO is artificial insemination for swine and large farm animals, such as cattle. This advanced breeding technique allows farmers to produce animals with improved genetic traits, resulting in healthier and higher-quality livestock. Artificial insemination is a cost-effective way to enhance breeding programs and increase genetic diversity, strengthening the regional livestock population. Healthier and more resilient animals are beneficial not only for individual farms but also for raising the overall quality of livestock in Nueva Vizcaya. Additionally, PVSO offers vaccination and deworming programs to protect animals from diseases and parasites. These preventative programs help keep the livestock population healthy and productive, which is essential for farmers' income and

the agricultural industry as a whole. PVSO also issues health certificates for animals being transported to other provinces to ensure they meet health requirements. This certification allows farmers to move their livestock safely and smoothly across regional borders, supporting local farmers while ensuring high standards of animal health and safety. The research locale for "PAAW: Portable Assistant for Animal Welfare, a Decision Support System for the Provincial Veterinary Services Office of Nueva Vizcaya" is located on the 3rd floor of the Agriculture building, Capitol Compound, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. This locale was our primary client, and it was essential for developing and testing the decision support system. The study aims to tailor the project to the Provincial Veterinary Services Office's needs, addressing their challenges and benefiting animal welfare in the region.

Research Participants

The participants in this study were carefully chosen through purposive sampling, specifically focusing on the employees of the Provincial Veterinary Services Office of Nueva Vizcaya to represent a diverse range of stakeholders engaged in its operations. The age qualification for the study participants was set between 24 and 60 years old. This range was selected to ensure a variety of experiences and perspectives and to identify any age-related vulnerabilities that might affect the operations and effectiveness of the PVSO. These stakeholders encompass key personnel from distinct divisions, including Administration, Livestock and Poultry Development, Regulatory and Monitoring, and Animal Health Care and Management. By including representatives from each division, the study aims to capture complete insights into the PVSO's functions, challenges, and strategies so as to facilitate a complete understanding of its operations and inform effective decision-making processes.

Administrative: The Administrative division serves as the pillar of the organization and is responsible for managing and coordinating its administrative functions. Within this division, the Administration Division is the one that maintains the organization's integrity, efficiency, and effectiveness.

Livestock and Poultry Development: The Livestock and Poultry Development division is dedicated to the progress and improvement of livestock and poultry activities within the province. This division is developing the growth and sustainability of the agricultural sector by focusing on the development and management of livestock and poultry resources. Comprising roles such as Farm Workers and Administrative Aides, the division is actively involved in supporting a wide range of activities related to animal husbandry, breeding, and production. Responsibilities within this division extend to providing technical assistance to farmers, implementing breeding programs aimed at improving genetic stock, and advocating for the adoption of best practices in livestock and poultry management.

Regulatory and Monitoring: This division is responsible for overseeing and enforcing regulations pertaining to livestock and poultry production. Key roles within this division include Veterinarians and Farm Workers who perform a variety of essential tasks. They conduct thorough inspections of farms to ensure adherence to health and safety standards, carry out disease surveillance to monitor and prevent outbreaks and address any regulatory issues that arise. Additionally, these professionals are involved in issuing necessary permits or licenses for animal-related activities, ensuring that all practices meet the required legal and ethical standards. Their work is crucial in maintaining the integrity and safety of the livestock and poultry industries.

Animal Health Care and Management Division: Animal Health Care and Management Division: This division is dedicated to the health and welfare of animals within the province. It comprises Veterinarians and Administrative Aides who provide a comprehensive range of healthcare services to animals, including the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of diseases. Their

responsibilities extend to conducting regular vaccinations, health screenings, and implementing quarantine measures to control the spread of infectious diseases. Additionally, the division is actively involved in promoting animal welfare and encouraging responsible pet ownership through public education and community outreach programs.

Software Development

The adoption of the Rapid Application Development (RAD) methodology is a practical approach for the development of PAAW, a portable assistant for animal welfare, a decision support system for the provincial veterinary services office of Nueva Vizcaya. This methodology allows developers to swiftly iterate and update software without having to start from scratch. This helps to ensure that the final product is of higher quality and meets the needs of the end-users (Kissflow, 2024). The RAD methodology, which prioritizes user participation, iterative development, and rapid prototyping, is a process-oriented approach that seeks to deliver software development that is both fast and high-quality. As such, it serves as an appropriate foundation for the creation of PAAW. Though frequently mistaken for a specific model, the idea behind RAD is that there is a benefit to treating software projects like clay rather than steel, which allows them to be tested and refined rather than going through the detailed planning and design phases associated with traditional development models (OUTSYSTEMS, 2024).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Section 1. Current Problem of the Provincial Veterinary Service Office (PVSO) Based on their Current Practices

1.1 Data Management

a. Reliance on Paper-Based Systems

According to the respondents, the Provincial Veterinary Services Office (PVSO) still relies mostly on paper-based methods for managing service requests, record-keeping, and reporting. Clients must come to the office in person to fill out and sign forms for various services, which makes the process slow, difficult, and more likely to make mistakes. This system also adds more work for the staff, causing delays and requests more efficiently and reducing these issues.

b. Manual Data Entry and Record-Keeping

Another major problem, as reported by the respondents, is the manual process used for entering data and creating reports. Many reports, such as inventory, utilization, inspection, and accomplishment reports, are done manually using Microsoft Excel. This approach is time-consuming and often results in human errors, like incorrect data entry or calculation mistakes, which can affect the accuracy of reports and slow down decision-making.

c. Difficulty in Finding and Accessing Information

It is also challenging to quickly find and access important documents. The current system relies on storing printed forms and reports, which makes it hard to find critical information quickly, especially in urgent situations. This lack of an organized digital system slows down the PVSO's ability to respond to problems and increases the workload on staff. A more effective digital system is needed to store and retrieve data quickly.

d. Delays in Analyzing Data and Reporting

The current manual processes also cause delays in analyzing data and creating reports. After field activities, data has to be manually collected, recorded, and analyzed, which slows down the whole reporting process. This delay affects the PVS0's ability to provide timely insights and take necessary actions. An automated system for collecting and analyzing data would make the office more responsive.

e. High Administrative Workload Due to Manual Processes

Manual handling of documents adds a heavy workload for PVS0 staff. Tasks like keeping records, compiling reports, and managing requests are all done by hand, which takes a lot of time and effort. This heavy workload prevents the team from focusing on more important tasks and reduces overall productivity. An automated and integrated system could help streamlining these tasks, cut down on workload, and improve service delivery.

1.2 Decision-Making on the Gathered Data

a. Field Reports

Each division, Livestock and Poultry Development, Regulatory and Monitoring, and Animal Health Care and Management, collects detailed information through their fieldwork. This data provides insights into various aspects such as animal production efficiency, regulatory compliance, and animal health status. Decision-makers rely on this data to formulate strategies, address issues, and improve operational effectiveness across the division. However, the current manual process of compiling and validating these field reports can lead to delays and errors, which may impact the accuracy and timeliness of decisions, affecting the effectiveness of programs and services. Therefore, there is a significant need for an automated system that not only streamlines the data entry and consolidation process but also ensures that decision-makers have access to accurate and timely information, thereby enhancing the overall decision-making process at the PVS0.

b. Inventory Reports

Effective decision-making at the PVS0 relies on accurate and timely inventory data. The two primary inventory reports, the Monthly Inventory and Utilization Report and the IT Equipment Inventory Report, provide essential information on the stock levels and condition of supplies and equipment. This data helps guide decisions related to ordering supplies, managing stock levels, and maintaining equipment.

The current process of managing inventory data using Microsoft Excel can lead to inaccuracies due to manual data entry and tracking. Errors in these reports can result in poor decision-making, such as understocking or overstocking items and mismanagement of IT equipment. To improve decision-making, it is crucial to ensure that inventory data is accurate and up-to-date. An automated inventory management system could enhance the accuracy of inventory records, streamline data entry, and provide real-time insights, thereby supporting better resource allocation and more effective operational planning.

Section 2. System Developed to Solve this Problem

To better manage and streamline field reports at the PVS0, PAAW was designed to enhance the management of Field Reports by providing a system for remote data input through digital forms that align with existing document formats. This approach allows field workers to enter information directly from the field, reducing errors and speeding up the reporting process. The system includes a centralized database that securely stores all collected data, ensuring easy retrieval and protection

against data loss. To further support efficient operations, PAAW offers a system for permission management based on the specific needs of each division, controlling data access according to user roles. It also enables the printing of forms and handles various requests efficiently, providing a system developed for managing field activities and improving overall operational effectiveness at the PVS0.

PAAW provides a system to streamline the process of managing client forms. It allows for the distribution of software to clients, enabling remote data input through digital versions of preexisting request forms. Clients can submit these forms based on the specific services they require, ensuring that all necessary information is accurately captured. Once submitted, PAAW facilitates the distribution of filled-out and approved request forms to the relevant divisions for further processing. All data is securely stored in a centralized database, ensuring easy access, efficient management, and protection against data loss.

To improve inventory management, the PAAW automated the handling of requisition forms. This meant that requests for new supplies or adjustments were processed electronically rather than through manual forms. By automating these requisition forms, PAAW streamlined how inventory needs were recorded and tracked, reducing errors and saving time. Additionally, all inventory data, including information from the Monthly Inventory and Utilization Report, was stored in a centralized database. This centralized storage made it easy to access and manage inventory records, ensuring that the data was accurate and up-to-date. The automated system helped maintain proper stock levels and ensured efficient use of resources across the PVS0. PAAW streamlined monthly report consolidation by automating the process of combining data from field reports. This automation replaced the manual effort previously needed to aggregate and format data from various divisions, reducing the time and potential errors involved. With automated data consolidation, PAAW ensured that all relevant information was accurately compiled into a single, comprehensive report. Data from the consolidated reports was stored in a central database, providing an organized and easily accessible repository for all monthly reports. This central storage facilitated efficient data management and allowed for quick retrieval of historical data, which was essential for trend analysis and reporting. Additionally, PAAW supported the printing of finalized reports, enabling the production of hard copies for distribution or further review. This integrated approach enhanced the accuracy and efficiency of report consolidation, delivering timely and reliable insights for the PVS0.

Section 3: What is the extent to which the PAAW decision support system complies with ISO 25010

The developed PAAW job posting and matching application was evaluated using ISO 25010 Software Quality Standards. This evaluation aimed to assess the system's adherence to criteria such as functional suitability, performance efficiency, compatibility, usability, reliability, security, maintainability, and portability. The assessment focused on confirming that the application effectively meets functional requirements, performs efficiently, is compatible across different platforms, provides a user-friendly experience, maintains high reliability and security, is easy to maintain, and demonstrates portability.

Table 1
Functional Suitability

	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
Functional Suitability			
Functional completeness	4.71	Very Great Extent	The measure described in the item is compliant to a very great extent or OUTSTANDING
Functional correctness	4.47	Very Great Extent	
Functional appropriateness	4.35	Very Great Extent	

Functional completeness measures the extent to which a system or software covers all specified tasks and user objectives. In this case, the rating of 4.71 suggests that the system is compliant to a very great extent in fulfilling all specified tasks and user objectives. This is a positive indication that the system is comprehensive in addressing user needs.

In summary, these results indicate that the system being evaluated performs exceptionally well in terms of functional completeness, correctness, and appropriateness, with ratings all above 4 on the provided scale. These high ratings reflect a system that effectively meets user needs, delivers accurate results, and is well-suited for its intended purpose.

Table 2
Performance Efficiency

	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
Performance Efficiency			
Time Behavior	4.47	Very Great Extent	The measure described in the item is compliant to a great extent up to very great extent
Resource utilization	4.12	Great Extent	
Capacity	3.88	Great Extent	

Performance efficiency measures how effectively a system operates within the specified time, resource, and capacity limits. In this case, a rating of 4.47 for time behavior suggests the system is compliant to a very great extent in meeting time-related performance requirements. A rating of 4.12 for resource utilization indicates a great extent of efficiency in managing resources effectively, while a score of 3.88 for capacity reflects a great extent of compliance in handling workloads.

In summary, these results suggest that the system performs well in terms of performance efficiency, particularly in time behavior, with good resource and capacity management.

Table 3
Compatibility

	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
Compatibility			
Co-existence	4.47	Very Great Extent	The measure described in the item is compliant to a very great extent or OUTSTANDING
Interoperability	4.41	Very Great Extent	

Compatibility measures how well a system interacts with other systems or software within its environment. A rating of 4.47 for co-existence suggests that the system is compliant to a very great extent, operating effectively alongside other systems and reflecting outstanding performance. Similarly, a rating of 4.41 for interoperability indicates compliance to a very great extent, showing the system's ability to exchange and utilize information efficiently.

In summary, under the overarching theme of compatibility, the table results demonstrate a system that excels in both co-existence and interoperability. Ratings for both dimensions surpass the 4-point threshold, indicating robust compatibility. These findings imply that the system can operate efficiently in shared environments and communicate effectively with other components or systems, fostering seamless interactions and data exchange.

Table 4
Usability

	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
Usability			
Appropriateness recognizability	4.53	Very Great Extent	The measure described in the item is compliant to a very great extent or OUTSTANDING
Learnability	4.41	Very Great Extent	
Operability	4.71	Very Great Extent	
User error protection	4.41	Very Great Extent	
User interface aesthetics	4.53	Very Great Extent	
Accessibility	4.53	Very Great Extent	

Usability measures how effectively a system supports users in achieving their goals. A rating of 4.53 for appropriateness recognizability, user interface aesthetics, and accessibility reflects compliance to a very great extent, ensuring clarity, visual appeal, and inclusivity. Learnability and user error protection, both rated 4.41, highlight ease of learning and reliable error prevention. The 4.71 rating for operability indicates exceptional user control.

In summary, the table results indicate a system that excels in multiple dimensions. High ratings across all dimensions suggest that the system is user-centric, appropriately aligned with user needs, easy to learn and operate, and aesthetically pleasing. Furthermore, it accommodates a diverse user base and provides robust error protection.

Table 5
Reliability

	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
Reliability			
Maturity	4.35	Very Great Extent	The measure described in the item is compliant to a very great extent or OUTSTANDING
Availability	4.53	Very Great Extent	
Fault Tolerance	4.47	Very Great Extent	
Recoverability	4.35	Very Great Extent	

Reliability measures the system's ability to perform consistently under specific conditions. A rating of 4.35 for maturity and recoverability suggests the system is compliant to a very great extent, demonstrating stability and the ability to recover from failures effectively. A 4.53 rating for availability reflects outstanding system uptime, while a 4.47 rating for fault tolerance highlights its ability to handle errors without failure.

In summary, within the domain of reliability, the table results portray a system that excels in multiple dimensions. High ratings across all dimensions suggest that the system is reliable under normal operation, consistently available, resilient in the face of faults, and capable of effective data recovery.

Table 6
Security

	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
Security			
Confidentiality	4.76	Very Great Extent	The measure described in the item is compliant to a very great extent or OUTSTANDING
Integrity	4.53	Very Great Extent	
Non-repudiation	4.47	Very Great Extent	
Accountability	4.56	Very Great Extent	
Authenticity	4.65	Very Great Extent	

Security measures the system's ability to protect sensitive data and ensure trustworthiness. A rating of 4.76 for confidentiality indicates outstanding protection of sensitive information. The 4.53 rating for integrity reflects strong data consistency, while non-repudiation (4.47) ensures

accountability for actions. A 4.56 rating for accountability highlights effective tracking of user actions, and a 4.65 rating for authenticity ensures the system verifies user identities to a very great extent.

In summary, within the domain of security, the table results depict a system that excels in multiple dimensions. High ratings across all dimensions suggest that the system effectively protects data confidentiality and integrity, supports non-repudiation, maintains accountability, and ensures the authenticity of user identities.

Table 7
Maintainability

	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
Maintainability			
Modularity	4.24	Very Great Extent	The measure described in the item is compliant as it ranges to great extent up to very great extent
Reusability	4.41	Very Great Extent	
Analyzability	4.29	Very Great Extent	
Modifiability	4.41	Very Great Extent	
Testability	4.06	Great Extent	

Maintainability measures the ease with which a system can be maintained and updated. A rating of 4.24 for modularity reflects compliance to a very great extent, indicating the system's components are well-organized for maintenance. Reusability (4.41) and modifiability (4.41) highlight the system's ability to adapt and reuse components effectively. Analyzability (4.29) shows that the system is easily analyzed for maintenance needs. A rating of 4.06 for testability indicates a great extent of ease in testing the system.

In summary, within the domain of maintainability, the table results portray a system that performs well across multiple dimensions. While there is room for improvement in modularity, the system excels in reusability, analyzability, modifiability, and testability.

Table 8
Portability

	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
Portability			
Adaptability	4.29	Very Great Extent	The measure described in the item is compliant to a great extent up to very great extent
Installability	4.35	Very Great Extent	
Replaceability	4.18	Great Extent	

Portability measures the system's ability to operate across different environments. A rating of 4.29 for adaptability indicates compliance to a very great extent, reflecting the system's strong ability to adjust to different conditions. Installability (4.35) shows the system can be easily installed

in various environments. A rating of 4.18 for replaceability reflects a great extent of compliance, suggesting the system can be replaced or updated with relative ease.

In summary, within the domain of portability, the table results depict a system that excels in all three dimensions. High ratings across these dimensions suggest that the system is highly adaptable to changing environments and technologies, can be easily installed and uninstalled, and serves as a suitable replacement for other software products in the same environment.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The researchers have concluded that addressing the current challenges faced by the PVS0 in managing field reports, client forms, and inventory requires the implementation of an automated solution. The system developed addresses the inefficiencies and mistakes caused by manual processes. It allows field workers and clients to enter data directly through digital forms, reducing errors and speeding up the reporting process. The system also automates inventory tracking and consolidates reports, storing all data securely in one place for easy access. It includes permission management to control who can access sensitive data based on roles. By improving data accuracy and making operations more efficient, this approach helped the PVS0 manage resources better, improve decision-making, and enhance overall service delivery. The researchers conclude that the system is compliant with ISO 25010:2015 based on the result of the system assessment.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions above, here are some suggestions/recommendations:

1. Expand the scope to include collaboration with Municipal Agriculture Offices (MAGROs).
2. Develop an API to allow integration between PAAW and a future MAGRO system for animal industry management.
3. Utilize TypeScript in coding to streamline development and maintain ease of understanding for future developers.
4. Enhance the charting and analysis features for more comprehensive data insights.
5. Reduce the number of forms by creating custom forms for the system in coordination with PVS0 and removing any duplicate forms.

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